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Total weight befor:10.29330 g
 Sample weight befor:4.55630 g
 Total weight after:10.29330 g
 Sample weight after:4.55630:g
 Weight difference:0.00000 g

ANALYTICAL PARAMETERS

Reference:I
 Reduction:Small
 Reference volume:20.96613 cc
 Cell volume:25.12102 cc
 Filler volume:0.00000 cc
 Repeated analyses no.:1
 Flow cleaning time:20:sec
 Number of cleaning cycles:6
 Sample cleaning time:15 sec
 Atm stabilization time:20 sec
 Restriction delta pressure:0.50000 bar
 Equilibrium delta pressure:0.01000 bar
 Equilibrium delta time:10 sec
 Standard deviation %:0.500 %
 No. of good measurements:3
 No. of max. measurements:30
 High Percision:No
 Temperature set:20.00 °C

RESULTS

Average Sample Volume:1.04320 cc
 Volume Standard Deviation:0.00458 cc
 % Standard Deviation on Volume:0.43868 %
 Average Sample Density:4.36768 g/cc
 Density Standard Deviation:0.01913 g/cc
 % Standard Deviation on Density:0.43807 %
 Average Sample Density after:4.36768 g/cc

MEASUREMENT RAW DATA

Patmh	Prh	Pch	Temp	Volume	Aver.Vol	Aver.Dev.
bar	bar	bar	°C	cc	cc	cc
1.02619	2.00099	1.47999	19.98	1.05011	1.05011	0.00000
1.02611	2.00115	1.47889	19.98	0.93733	0.99372	0.07975
1.02614	2.00104	1.47982	19.99	1.03395	1.00713	0.06098
1.02607	2.00151	1.47992	19.99	1.02570	0.99900	0.05356
1.02609	2.00145	1.48004	19.98	1.03922	1.03296	0.00681
1.02602	2.00111	1.47987	19.98	1.04217	1.03570	0.00878
1.02606	2.00109	1.47995	19.98	1.04820	1.04320	0.00458